

Densities and Apparent Molar Volume of Benzimidazole in Methanol + Water Pure & Binary Solvent Mixtures

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Abstract: Benzimidazole is an important pharmacophore in medicinal chemistry. Benzimidazoles are having a many therapeutic uses like antibacterial, antifungal, analgesics, antitumor, antiparasitic, antihistamine, and antiviral. Using bicapillary pycnometer densities of Benzimidazole in methanol with water were measured over the entire composition range at temperatures from 293.15 to 313.15 K. Densities of the saturated solution of benzimidazole in a pure and binary mixture of solvents were measured at mentioned temperature. This density data was used to calculate apparent molar volume. The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) values for all solutions in pure solvents or in mixed solvent increases with the increase of temperature. The density of benzimidazole in pure water solution decreases slightly with the increase in temperature but for pure methanol solution it increases with increase in temperature.

Keywords: Density, Apparent molar volume, Benzimidazole, Mathanol

Introduction:

Benzimidazole is aromatic heterocyclic compound, having molecular formula $C_7H_6N_2$. It is bicyclic compound and consists of a fusion of imidazole and benzene. In medicinal chemistry, benzimidazole is privileged structure and one of the important pharmacophore. In many of therapeutic activity, it has an important role such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiulcer, analgesic, antihypertensive, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antihelmintic and anticancer [1].

U. Domanska and M.K. Kozłowska [2] studied solubilities, density, partition coefficient and surface tension for imidazoles + n-decane/ octan-1-ol/ water, temperature range used for measurements were from 270 K to melting temperature of the compound.

M. Das et al. [3] worked on benzimidazolium dichromate and 2-methyl imidazolium dichromate and measured viscosity and density at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K, in water and its mixture with DMSO.

Benzimidazole is a very important compound for synthesis of pharmaceuticals and physical properties such as density need to be studied systematically. Therefore it is planned to measure the density of benzimidazole in pure water, methanol, and in mixed solvents water + methanol at temperatures ranges from 293.15 to 313.15 K.

Materials and method:

Materials:

Benzimidazole was provided by Spectrochem with purity 99 %, Methanol was provided by Fisher Scientific with purity 99.5 %

Method:

In the present work a bicapillary pycnometer having 15 c.c. bulk volumes were used for measurement of density. Chromic acid was used to clean the capillary of the pycnometer. Then pycnometer was further washed with distilled water and acetone and it was dried with hot air blower. Then it was accurately weighed on Scale-Tec balance having a sensitivity of 1×10^{-4} mg. For calibration of the pycnometer triple distilled water was used. About 15 - 20 ml of water was taken in a beaker and is filled to the limb 'P' of the pycnometer. During filling of water to the pycnometer, air bubble was avoided. Water filled up to mark 'R' in limb 'Q' by capillary action. Pycnometer was weighed again.

In the glass-sided thermostat, pycnometer was mounted vertically. Thermostat temperature was controlled within 0.01° C. The height of water i.e. h_1 and h_2 in limb 'P and Q' were measured at all experimental temperatures (293.15 to 313.15) K by using a travelling microscope. From the known densities of water at a various temperature and the weights of the water taken in the pycnometer, corresponding volumes of water were calculated. The height ($h_1 + h_2$) versus volume of water plot yields a straight line. The slope and intercept values are obtained by using least square method which is used for calculating the density of liquids [4, 5].

From thermostat, pycnometer was removed. It is cleaned as per procedure mentioned above. After this experimental liquid was filled in the pycnometer and it is mounted vertically in the thermostat. For finding the total height ($h_1 + h_2$) at different temperatures for experimental liquids, the same procedure was repeated. From their total height, the corresponding volume of liquids under investigation was obtained from the calibration curve and the corresponding densities thus determined.

The repetition of measurements of density for each experimental liquid was carried out three to four times and the average result was calculated [6-16].

Result and Discussion:

Tables 1 show molalities (m), densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (Φ_V) of benzimidazole for various initial mole fractions (x_C^0) of methanol in water at temperatures (293.15 to 313.15) K. Figures 1 show plot of densities versus temperature (T/K), for benzimidazole + water + methanol with the initial mole fraction of methanol.

Apparent molar volume (Φ_V) is calculated by using equation (1). From tables 1, it is observed that Φ_V values are positive for benzimidazole pure solvents, water, methanol solutions and binary mixtures of water with methanol solutions at 293.15 to 313.15 K. The apparent molar volume (Φ_V) values for all solutions in pure solvents or in mixed solvent increases with the increase of temperature. The density of benzimidazole in pure water solution decreases slightly with the increase in temperature but for pure methanol solution it increases with increase in temperature.

Table 1: Molalities (m), densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (Φ_V) of benzimidazole for various initial mole fractions, (x_C^0), of methanol at temperatures (293.15 to 313.15) K.

T/K	x_C^0	m /mol.kg ⁻¹	$\rho \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg.m ⁻³	$\Phi_V \cdot 10^6$ /m ³ .mol ⁻¹
293.15	0.0000	0.0402	0.9988	87.0558
	0.0588	0.0574	0.9819	96.7923
	0.1232	0.0924	0.9676	97.5386
	0.1942	0.1786	0.9545	99.5242
	0.2726	0.3734	0.9418	100.2235
	0.3599	0.7297	0.9308	100.0076
	0.4575	1.2662	0.9224	100.4631
	0.5675	1.8985	0.9155	99.3635
	0.6922	2.5596	0.9070	99.0072
	0.8350	3.1104	0.8985	96.7302
1.0000	3.5366	0.8863	94.5017	
295.15	0.0000	0.0414	0.9980	94.1287
	0.0588	0.0594	0.9816	93.9084
	0.1232	0.1010	0.9673	94.9722
	0.1942	0.1978	0.9539	100.2995
	0.2726	0.4036	0.9411	101.0295
	0.3599	0.8049	0.9302	101.4671
	0.4575	1.3630	0.9229	100.6753
	0.5675	2.0225	0.9163	99.6268
	0.6922	2.6973	0.9080	99.1606
	0.8350	3.2476	0.8999	96.7100
1.0000	3.6783	0.8876	94.5516	

298.15	0.0000	0.0443	0.9973	95.7449
	0.0588	0.0672	0.9807	98.7835
	0.1232	0.1171	0.9665	95.7380
	0.1942	0.2263	0.9529	101.0476
	0.2726	0.4654	0.9404	101.5404
	0.3599	0.9039	0.9304	101.3179
	0.4575	1.5174	0.9237	100.8560
	0.5675	2.2335	0.9182	99.7229
	0.6922	2.9271	0.9102	99.1897
	0.8350	3.5147	0.9020	97.1851
	1.0000	3.9151	0.8895	94.8757
300.15	0.0000	0.0481	0.9969	95.2409
	0.0588	0.0743	0.9805	96.6614
	0.1232	0.1256	0.9656	98.3610
	0.1942	0.2471	0.9524	100.8994
	0.2726	0.5096	0.9401	101.8388
	0.3599	0.9754	0.9306	101.3390
	0.4575	1.6469	0.9247	101.1090
	0.5675	2.3838	0.9195	99.8251
	0.6922	3.1157	0.9116	99.5194
	0.8350	3.6721	0.9035	97.1972
	1.0000	4.0781	0.8910	95.0233
303.15	0.0000	0.0546	0.9962	96.4315
	0.0588	0.0833	0.9796	97.9086
	0.1232	0.1464	0.9649	98.2165
	0.1942	0.2850	0.9515	101.0729
	0.2726	0.5827	0.9395	102.2932
	0.3599	1.1144	0.9312	101.5928
	0.4575	1.8424	0.9261	101.3024
	0.5675	2.6286	0.9217	99.9879
	0.6922	3.3573	0.9148	99.0536
	0.8350	3.9638	0.9062	97.4359
	1.0000	4.3624	0.8938	95.1646
305.15	0.0000	0.0583	0.9956	98.0354
	0.0588	0.0916	0.9788	100.7168
	0.1232	0.1620	0.9642	100.2125
	0.1942	0.3134	0.9508	102.0501
	0.2726	0.6426	0.9395	102.3636
	0.3599	1.2098	0.9316	101.8222
	0.4575	1.9927	0.9273	101.4010
	0.5675	2.8176	0.9234	100.1531
	0.6922	3.5925	0.9165	99.5642

	0.8350	4.1694	0.9081	97.6369
	1.0000	4.5544	0.8954	95.4408
308.15	0.0000	0.0647	0.9946	99.5388
	0.0588	0.1034	0.9780	101.5519
	0.1232	0.1836	0.9630	101.9294
	0.1942	0.3653	0.9500	102.5036
	0.2726	0.7436	0.9396	102.3088
	0.3599	1.3861	0.9329	101.8652
	0.4575	2.2286	0.9302	100.9896
	0.5675	3.1140	0.9264	100.2734
	0.6922	3.9150	0.9194	99.7954
	0.8350	4.4897	0.9110	97.9079
	1.0000	4.8512	0.8983	95.5974
	310.15	0.0000	0.0713	0.9942
0.0588		0.1128	0.9774	100.7856
0.1232		0.2022	0.9627	100.9699
0.1942		0.4043	0.9495	102.7629
0.2726		0.8228	0.9396	102.7107
0.3599		1.5167	0.9342	101.6362
0.4575		2.4452	0.9315	101.6371
0.5675		3.3469	0.9284	100.5508
0.6922		4.1817	0.9200	100.8250
0.8350		4.7288	0.9136	97.9016
1.0000		5.0778	0.9001	95.9100
313.15		0.0000	0.0779	0.9931
	0.0588	0.1286	0.9764	101.7035
	0.1232	0.2346	0.9616	101.5538
	0.1942	0.4726	0.9494	102.2223
	0.2726	0.9520	0.9405	102.2677
	0.3599	1.7555	0.9361	102.0381
	0.4575	2.6915	0.9347	101.0499
	0.5675	3.6923	0.9332	99.9737
	0.6922	4.5713	0.9261	97.5396
	0.8350	5.0597	0.9168	97.8921
	1.0000	5.4239	0.9034	96.0821

Figure 1: Plot of density versus temperature (T/K) for benzimidazole + water + methanol system with initial mole fraction.

The density of a liquid or liquid mixture is calculated as the mass per unit volume and is generally expressed in CGS as $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ or more appropriately in SI as $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Apparent molar volume [17] can be calculated by using following equation (1).

$$\Phi_V = \frac{1}{m} \left[\frac{1000 + mM}{\rho} - \frac{1000}{\rho_0} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, m = Molality, M = Molecular weight of solute, ρ_0 = Density of pure water or solvent system, ρ = Density of solution

Conclusion:

Densities of the saturated solution of benzimidazole in a pure and binary mixture of solvents were measured at 293.15 to 313.15 K. This density data was used to calculate apparent molar volume. The apparent molar volume (Φ_V) values for all solutions in pure solvents or in mixed solvent increases with the increase of temperature. The density of benzimidazole in pure water solution decreases slightly with the increase in temperature but for pure methanol solution it increases with increase in temperature.

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